

Brand Awareness & Marketing Campaign for Nilkamal

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ABSTRACT

This paper is commissioned to examine the "BRAND AWARENESS & MARKETING CAMPAIGN FOR NILKAMAL." This paper has various aspects of Marketing function and operation by applying theoretical knowledge and concepts to the best. The main research problem was to acknowledge about the brand awareness among the customers and to find out the preferences of the products and satisfaction level regarding the same. Hence, the methodology was used during the research was collection of data through primary and secondary both and the basic instrument in order to study about the subject was questionnaire. The major findings was that customers are aware about the brand and are preferring the products of the organization. The brand positioning is also good in the minds of the customers. But the frequency of purchasing of the product is not up to the mark. The organization should focus on the distribution channel, which will increase the awareness among the customers. Organization should also focus on the advertisement of their various products which can rapidly increase the sales of the organization. Therefore, the top management of the company should take marketing campaign into concern. Hence this will increase brand awareness.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Marketing Campaign, Brand Positioning, Distribution Channel, Advertisements.

INTRODUCTION

Nilkamal Limited is Asia's biggest plastic processor of formed items situated in Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. It is likewise world's biggest maker of shaped furnishings or moulded furniture. It has wide scope of items which is utilized in various segment and distinctive sort of industries. The running items contains Plastic Furniture, material handling crates and bins, infant table, center table, dining table, grower, rack, stool, mechanical beds, waste bins, protected cartons and so forth. Home is the retail division of Nilkamal Limited. The gathering directions showcase administration in India with five best in class fabricating offices in different states of India authorize with quality authentications like ISO 9001 and ISO 14000. The gathering has not constrained its assembling activities in India but rather have additionally run beyond Indian boundaries with its mastery in the field of plastics and has set up Joint venture producing offices in Sri Lanka with a pioneer of Sri Lankan market for Shaped Furnishings. The group has a wide array of products in plastic crates, maintenance products, plastic pallets, waste management products, road safety products, storage system etc. A Company's positioning and differentiation strategies must be changed as the product, market, and competitors change over the Product Life Cycle (PLC). In other words we can say that position of any brand is also decided by the graph of product life cycle.

Brand plays a critical job in the Product Life Cycle. Increasingly critical in this exchange, at those two points, is the thing that happens when you have declining product with a huge brand loyalty base and the use of their development to the outcome is a significantly sharp bend curve upward of adoption. Brand Positioning is the remaining of Brand in comparison with its competitors on the brains of client, prospect and different stakeholders.

FUNCTIONAL DEPARTMENTS OF THE ORGANIZATION

Now regarding the working of the company Nilkamal plastics has divided the entire working of the organization into various departments. Each department has a person in charge & many skilled workers for each of the respective

departments making the whole process a successful one. There are in all 150 efficient workers for the plant & they are divided into these departments. The various types of department in Nilkamal plastics are

1. ADMINISTRATIVE DEPARTMENT
2. ACCOUNTING DEPARTMENT
3. RAW MATERIAL DEPARTMENT
4. GRINDING & BLENDING DEPARTMENT
5. PRODUCTION & MAINTENANCE DEPARTMENT
6. QUALITY ASSURANCE DEPARTMENT
7. FABRICATION DEPARTMENT
8. DESIGN DEPARTMENT
9. ASSEMBLING & PACKING DEPARTMENT
10. DISPATCH DEPARTMENT

MATERIAL HANDLING

Material handling is an indispensable piece of any mechanical action. With developing business, a more noteworthy accentuation is laid on productivity, productivity just as resource conservation and biological conservation. Material handling assumes an exceptionally critical job in supporting effectiveness in money related and HR.

Today Nilkamal is the biggest maker of plastic cartons for different ventures running from automobiles, pharmaceutical, designing, electrical, materials, general stores, hardware, retail, Agribusiness, Fish, Neighborliness and Cooking and other associated business. We have kept up our validity through our steady endeavors that think about our business tie-ups as well as our quality affirmation. Being an ISO 9001: 2008 affirmed organization; we keep up quality principles directly from assembling to circulation.

Through our quality and redemption, we are one of the real exporters to Europe, USA, Center East, Far East, Africa and Asia.

SWOT ANALYSIS

SWOT analysis is an abbreviation for Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats and is an organized arranging strategy that assesses those four components of a task or business venture.

STRENGTH

- Reputed brand image of Nilkamal
- Quality of Nilkamal product
- Durability of Nilkamal products
- Reliability of brand
- Research & Development and innovation about new model and its uses
- Wide range of models
- Satisfying customers' needs
- Innovative models & colors' of Nilkamal products
- Effective & efficient management and work force

WEAKNESS

- Nilkamal crates has high prices as compared to its competitors
- Nilkamal concentrates more major users and less on minor users of crates
- Nilkamal is not able to properly communicate its various models, new innovation and its use to the customers
- Distribution channel of Nilkamal is weak in comparison to its competitors
- More innovation and R&D are required to improve quality and reduces prices

- Nilkamal doesn't provides proper sales promotion, schemes like discount and commissions to the agent.

OPPORTUNITY

- Capturing global business in terms of acquiring and serving international customers.
- Nilkamal can manufacture special trolley for invertors and battery.
- Special tables and stands for computer system and television etc can be manufactured.
- Small trolley can be manufactured for home and departmental stores.
- Nilkamal can manufacture folding crates in order to save floor space when not in use.
- New opportunities are arising due industrialization and globalization.

THREATS

- The competitors of Nilkamal, can tend to eat into the market share of Nilkamal with their much lower rate (i.e. price of crates).
- Quality is also comparable to that of Nilkamal products.
- Nilkamal will have to reduce the price of its crates and other products, otherwise it might lose its precious customers to its competitors.

STATEMENT & INTRODUCTION OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is the consciousness of the consumers when they have close and intimate knowledge of the product life and availability. Draws the attention towards Brand Recognition and Brand Recall.

Creation of awareness of brand is an important step in promotion and involvement of the new product. It is making the consumer more familiar about the products, features and quality etc. It actually creates a kind of existence in the minds of consumer due to the quality, features and services which make the consumer recall the products again and again.

Unique features and services add value to the products and help the consumers recognize it and keep a place into their conscious. It also helps in creating and increasing brand equity which ultimately help in increasing sale volume, profit increment etc.

There are two sorts of Brand Awareness:

- Aided Awareness
- Top of mind awareness(Immediate Brand Review)

Marketing Campaign

The moto of an organization or an outsider promoting organization are to build awareness for a specific item or administration, or to expand purchaser consciousness of a business or association. A promoting effort has a constrained term.

Steps to direct effective Marketing Campaign

1. Know how your marketing campaign fits into your showcasing plan.
2. Set the objectives of your marketing campaign.
3. Determine how you will gauge achievement.
4. Set the budget of your marketing campaign.

5. Choose your advertising techniques to speak with the consumers.
6. Create a course of events/activity plan.
7. Do it.
8. Measure your outcomes.
9. Follow up.

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To find out the satisfaction level of Nilkamal crates user.
- To have a comparative analysis of Nilkamal crates and bins of its competitor.
- To know the preferences of the customer.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Dr. Hsin Kuang Chi, 2009) This study was done to explore brand awareness on consumer purchase intention, it states that brand identity and recalling of brands are positively related to purchase intentions which signifies, the higher the brand awareness, the higher the purchase intention. It also reveals that action loyalty and affective loyalty are positively related to purchase intention. Its findings state that brand loyalty represents a repurchase commitment in the future purchase which consumers will not change their brand loyalty in any different situations and continue buying their favourite brands.

(Christian Homburg, 2010) This study was done on Brand awareness in business markets: When is it related to firm performance? and it focused on brand awareness because it is a key element of many B2B branding strategies. After the survey analysis of 300 B2B firms it was found that the

association between brand awareness and market performance is stronger in markets.

(Sharp, 2003) This study was done on management perceptions of the importance of brand awareness as an indication of advertising effects and it explains the study of attitude of many managers in the context of brand awareness. The finding of the study was managers consider unworthy and unimportant the idea of maintaining brand awareness. Also managers state that measuring and determining brand value is quite difficult.

(Prof. Dr. Muhammad Ehsan Malik, 2013) this study was done on importance of brand awareness and brand loyalty in assessing purchase intentions of consumer and found that development of brand awareness and brand loyalty is the requirement of the time and every managers of every business should consider it as an important factor and bring continuous improvements in the brands and promote it as it enhances the customer’s intentions of purchasing the products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY USED IN THE RESEARCH

- Type of research design selected: **Descriptive Research Design**
- Data collection method for primary data: **Questionnaire**
- Research Approach : **Direct Method**
- Sampling Area : **Gorakhpur**
- Sample unit: **Customer of Nilkamal Plastic**
- Sampling technique/method: **Convenience**

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Fig 1: Shows the percentage of user of different Plastic Brand

Fig 2: Shows the percentage of user of different Plastic Product

Fig 3: Shows the percentage of Basis of Purchasing Power

Fig 4: Shows the percentage of Product Meeting Customer Needs

Fig 5: Shows the percentage of Buyer of No. of Crates

Fig 6: Shows the Buying Behavior of Different Respondents

Fig 7: Shows the percentage of Customer Satisfaction Level

Fig 8: Shows the percentage of Awareness of Respondents through Different channels

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

- Majority of users of crates i.e. 39% of total user prefer Nilkamal crates. Then second and third preference is given to Prince & Supreme crates with 31% and 21%.
- Majority of user i.e. 60.81% of total are minor user of crates, they use less than 100 crates.
- Majority user prefers Multipurpose & Jumbo crates with 33% & 25%.
- The majority of user crates i.e. 100% prefer yearly purchase of crates.
- Majority of people prefer Price as basis for purchase with 42%.
- Majority of customer are price affecting buying behavior of crates.
- Majority of 48% of total purchase decision taken by owner.
- Majority of respondent 61% are satisfied with the performance of crates.

LIMITATIONS

Every pros have cons so as in my project, it faces some limitation; because of these limitations the required and necessary data to complete the project may not gathered in proper manner. The limitations which we observe were as follows:

- Few respondents don't co-operate with me in this survey.
- Most of respondents didn't have time for supporting me in filling Questionnaire.
- Respondents were not excited in providing detail personal information.
- At the pick time (Morning) some respondents didn't give the response due to rush.
- Those respondents who were not interested in buying the product, they were not in support in filling the Questionnaire.

CONCLUSION

Nilkamal Plastics and Nilkamal Furniture is a well-known name and people seem to identify any tools, table, chair, crates & bins as a Nilkamal Product. Quality & Price factor was found as one of the main reasons for customers to use its product. The other reason was found as their habit of using wooden crates and pallets. It will take time to shift those customers from using wooden to plastic.

About 90% of industry has showed a positive response towards the product. The project research shows that innovative products can give the spontaneous result if it is marketed well. The satisfaction level of customers regarding its product was up to the mark. The company is creating

brand image of furniture industry. The Nilkamal industry maintains the quality of product up to the mark.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Company should improve the promotional strategies of the product.
- The company should focus on advertisement so as to improve the brand image of the company.
- The company should provide high quality product so that 100% customers get satisfaction from the quality.
- The company should try to provide the concession of product, so that most of the customer purchases the product.
- The company should improve the quality of the product, so that the minimum problems are faced by the customer.
- Company should provide qualitative product so that they can use the product for maximum years.
- The company should focus on the distribution channel & transportation, so that the products are easily available to the customer.

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